

SHEAR AND BUCKLING STRENGTHENING OF STEEL BRIDGE GIRDER USING SMALL-DIAMETER CFRP STRANDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of a comprehensive research program undertaken to investigate the use of small-diameter CFRP strands for strengthening steel structures and bridges. The proposed CFRP strands are stitched together with a gap between the strands to allow the epoxy material to penetrate and cover the entire perimeter of each strand. Initially, the investigation examined the effectiveness of using these small-diameter CFRP strands to increase the flexural capacity of concrete-steel composite beams. The same fibres were also used to increase the buckling capacity of steel plates simulating typical steel web girders of bridges. The research extended to examine the proposed strengthening system to increase the shear capacity of steel plates. In general, research findings showed that the proposed system is extremely effective in strengthening steel structures and bridges and totally eliminated failure due to de-bonding which is commonly observed for CFRP laminates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the known benefits of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) materials, their use for retrofitting (strengthening and repair) of concrete structures and bridges has gained wide acceptance worldwide and became a common practice. This is attributed mainly due to the high modulus of elasticity of FRP material relative to concrete, and the extensive research conducted in this field. This led to the development of design guidelines adopted in codes for retrofitting of concrete structures and bridges with FRP. However, the use of FRP material for steel structures has not been very successful due to their low elastic moduli in comparison to steel. The production of high- and intermediate-elastic modulus Carbon FRP (CFRP) with elastic modulus higher than that of steel, offers a promising alternative for flexural and shear strengthening of steel structures and bridges [1].

Significant research has been conducted at NCSU to investigate the flexural strengthening of steel girders using high-modulus CFRP laminates [2, 3]. Experimental testing showed that the governing mode of failure was de-bonding of the high-modulus CFRP laminates. The low bonding capacity of the high-modulus CFRP laminates is attributed to the fact that the laminates are bonded to the substrate from once face only.

The recent development of small-diameter CFRP strands, provided in sheet configuration, is a promising alternative strengthening system for steel structures. The small-diameter CFRP strands are provided in sheet configuration as shown in Figure 1. The CFRP strands are approximately 1.0 mm (1/25 in.) in diameter and are stitched together leaving a gap between the strands. The gap between the strands allows each strand to be totally covered by the epoxy adhesive, resulting in an excellent bond mechanism. The new CFRP strands are high-strength, and produced with different elastic moduli in

the range of or higher than that of steel. Having CFRP strands provided in form of sheets is convenient also for field application [4].

Figure 1: Proposed small-diameter CFRP strands

2. FLEXURAL STRENGTHENING

To examine the effectiveness of the small-diameter CFRP strands for flexural strengthening of typical steel girders, five scaled steel-concrete composite beams were strengthened and tested under static loading to increase their flexural strength and stiffness. In addition, a control beam was tested without strengthening. The beams were 3350 mm (11 ft) long with a test span of 3050 mm (10 ft). All beams were tested in four-point bending configuration up to failure and were simply supported as shown in Figure 2. The steel beam was W-shape beam (W8x13), acting in composite action with a 533x66 mm (21x2.6 in.) reinforced concrete slab using shear studs on top flange of the steel beam [5].

Figure 2: Test setup for flexural testing of steel-concrete composite beams

Two different types of the CFRP strands with different elastic moduli were used in this study. The first type was Low-Modulus (LM) CFRP strand with an elastic modulus of 135 GPa (20,000 ksi) and a rupture strain of 1.7 percent. The second type was Intermediate-Modulus (IM) CFRP strand with an elastic modulus of 225 GPa (33,000 ksi) and a rupture strain of 1.0 percent. Two beams were strengthened with LM CFRP strands, using three layers (S3-LM) and four layers (S4-LM). Two beams were strengthened with IM CFRP strands, using three layers (S3-IM) and four layers (S4-IM). The CFRP strands were externally bonded to the bottom face of the lower steel flange as shown in Figure 3(a). The fifth beam (S4-LM-IM) was strengthened with both types of CFRP strands. Three layers of LM CFRP strands were bonded to the bottom face of lower flange and 2 layers of IM strands were bonded to the top face of the lower flange and the web as shown in Figure 3(b). The CFRP strands were bonded to the beams in an overhead application to simulate field working conditions.

Figure 3: Cross section details of the test specimens

Measured load-deflection at mid-span for all tested specimens is shown in Figure 4. Test results show that using CFRP strengthening system increases the stiffness within the elastic range and significantly increases the ultimate flexural capacity. Test results indicated also that for the same number of CFRP layers, IM CFRP is more effective in increasing the pre-yield and post-yield stiffness. However, their use may reduce the overall ductility due to the limited rupture strain in comparison to the LM CFRP. Test results indicated in general that the use of the small-diameter CFRP strand strengthening system is effective in increasing the yielding and ultimate load carrying capacity of steel members.

Figure 4: Applied load vs. mid-span deflection for tested specimens under static loading

The observed failure mode for the control beam and the beams strengthened with LM CFRP strands is due to crushing of the concrete at the top compression surface of the slab within the constant moment zone as shown in Figure 5(a). The measured average effectiveness of the LM CFRP strand was 80 percent of the rupture strain since the failure was due to crushing of the concrete. The beams strengthened with IM CFRP strands failed suddenly due to rupture of the CFRP strands. Beam S3-LM-IM failed due to rupture of the IM CFRP strands at the conjunction of the web as shown in Figure

5(b). Both modes of failures highlight the enhanced bonding strength of the small-diameter CFRP strand system to the steel substrate.

Figure 5: Failure modes a) Crushing of the concrete slab, b) Rupture of the IM CFRP strands

Based on the behavior observed from the six specimens tested under static loading, LM CFRP strands was selected to be the optimal strengthening system since it provided a significant increase in the flexural strength while showing a ductile behavior. The failure mode was crushing of the concrete slab which is a desirable failure mode for steel-concrete composite beams.

3. UNIAXIAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTHENING

Shear capacity of flexural members should also be increased to match the increased of the flexural capacity. Shear strength of steel girders with slender webs is typically controlled by the shear capacity of web. To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed small-diameter CFRP strands for shear strengthening of steel beams, their buckling behavior and the ability to undergo associated large deformations were initially investigated [6].

The experimental program used to study the effectiveness of the proposed CFRP strands in increasing the buckling capacity consisted of two phases. The first phase included testing of fourteen steel plates with different slenderness ratio (height-to-thickness) ranged from 48 to 154 under uniaxial compression load. Eight steel plates were strengthened with High-Modulus (HM) CFRP strands. The remaining six specimens were un-strengthened and used as control specimen. Two plates were strengthened without applying low-modulus polyurea putty to study the effect of putty on de-bonding capacity of the CFRP strands. The second phase identified the most effective type of CFRP strands among the three types of CFRP strands eith Low-Modulus (LM), Intermediate-Modulus (IM) and High-Modulus (HM) subjected to uniaxial compression load. The measured material properties of the three different types of CFRP strands are given in Table 1. Eighteen steel plates were tested using two selected slenderness ratios of 77 and 154. The effectiveness of using different reinforcement ratio of CFRP materials was also investigated by applying one and two layers of CFRP strands.

CFRP Strand	Rupture Strain	Rupture Stress	Elastic Modulus
	mm/mm (in./in.)	MPa (ksi)	MPa (ksi)
Low-Modulus(LM)	0.0168	2,353 (341)	140,253 (20,342)
Intermediate-Modulus (IM)	0.0104	2,220 (322)	212,752 (30,857)
High-Modulus (HM)	0.0032	806 (117)	255,430 (37,047)

Table 1: Material Properties of Small-Diameter CFRP strands

The test setup used for the concentric uniaxial compression applied to steel plates is shown in Figure 6. The test setup was designed to be a self-reacting A-frame. The test plates were welded at

both ends to high-strength steel tubes (sleeves), with an inner diameter of 152 mm (6 in.) and thickness of 13 mm (1/2 in.). Two 150 mm (6 in.) diameter, high-strength, chrome-painted steel pins were greased and inserted inside the sleeves. The sleeves were able to freely rotate around the two pins and thus providing boundary conditions resembling hinged-hinged end conditions. The pins were loaded by two high-strength steel pre-stressing bars and two hydraulic jacks. The supporting A-frame was tied down to the strong floor at four points to ensure stability of the frame during testing. The applied load was measured using load cells placed between the hydraulic jacks and the pins. Longitudinal strains in the test plates were measured using electrical resistance strain gages. A total of eight strain gauges were attached to strengthened specimens at mid-height. Four strain gauges were attached to the base steel before application of the strengthening system. The remaining four strain gauges were attached to the outer surface of the CFRP strand sheets after curing of the epoxy resin. Lateral deformations at both ends and mid-height of test plates were measured using string potentiometers. Optotrak Certus® motion capture system was also used to measure the overall deflected shape of the test specimen over their entire heights along at the centerline of the plate.

Figure 6: Test setup for uniaxial compression testing of plates

Buckling load for strengthened plates was compared to the buckling load of control un-strengthened plates. Test results of Phase I are given in Table 2. The measured percentage increase indicates clearly that bonding of HM CFRP strands to the steel plates increased the buckling capacity up to 60 percent. Test results indicate also that the effectiveness of the strengthening system increases by increasing the slenderness ratio. Furthermore, results indicated that all of the tested specimens experienced elastic buckling. It was observed that there were excellent bond characteristics between the steel and the small-diameter CFRP strands. There were no signs of de-bonding observed during the testing up to buckling on either the compression or tension faces of the specimens. The presence and absence of the polyurea putty did not have any obvious contributions to the bond characteristics.

Plate Designation	h	t	h/t	Strengthening	Polyurea Putty	Buckling Load	
	mm (in.)	mm (in.)				kN (kip)	Increase (%)
I-24-1/2-U	610 (24)	13 (1/2)	48	NO	-	645 (145)	-
I-24-1/2-S-P				YES	YES	787 (177)	22
I-24-3/8-U		10 (3/8)	64	NO	-	374 (84)	-
I-24-3/8-S-P				YES	YES	430 (97)	15
I-24-5/16-U		8 (5/16)	77	NO	-	210 (47)	-
I-24-5/16-S-P				YES	YES	295 (66)	40
I-24-5/16-S				YES	NO	325 (73)	55
I-48-1/2-U	1220 (48)	13 (1/2)	96	NO	-	112 (25)	-
I-48-1/2-S-P				YES	YES	176 (39)	56
I-48-3/8-U		10 (3/8)	128	NO	-	62 (14)	-
I-48-3/8-S-P				YES	YES	89 (20)	43
I-48-5/16-U		8 (5/16)	154	NO	-	58 (13)	-
I-48-5/16-S-P				YES	YES	76 (17)	31
I-48-5/16-S				YES	NO	93 (21)	61

Table 2: Test results summary of specimens in Phase I of compressive strengthening

Test results of phase I revealed that initial out-of-straightness and imperfections have an effect on the behavior of the specimen and thus the results of the test. Based on this observation, it was decided for Phase II, to use the same steel plates as control specimens prior to applying the CFRP strengthening system in order to compare the same plate before and after strengthening.

The applied load versus longitudinal steel strain and net lateral deflection at mid-height for the plates with slenderness ratio of 77 are shown in Figure 7(a), (b), and (c) for LM, IM, and HM CFRP materials, respectively. In each figure, behavior of one layer of CFRP and two layers of CFRP is compared to the control un-strengthened specimen. The results indicate that the addition of the CFRP strengthening systems increased the initial lateral stiffness of the specimens. Furthermore, the state of stress in the steel is reduced by adding the second layer of CFRP strengthening system.

(a)

Figure 7: Applied load vs. longitudinal steel strain and net lateral deformation of the plates with slenderness ratio 77

Figure 8 depicts the percent increase in buckling loads for the plates with slenderness ratio of 77 and 154 with different CFRP strand types and reinforcement ratios. It is clear that increasing the number of layers of CFRP strands increases the buckling load. Furthermore, high elastic modulus, HM CFRP strands are more effective in increasing the buckling load of a specimen. Test results indicated that the CFRP strengthening systems become more effective by increasing the slenderness ratio of the steel plate. It should be noted that no signs of de-bonding were observed on the compression or the tension faces of the test plates.

Figure 8: Buckling load percentage increase of plates strengthened with one and two layers of HM, IM, and LM CFRP strands, a) $h/t = 77$, b) $h/t = 154$

4. SHEAR STRENGTHENING OF STEEL WEB GIRDERS

The research is extended to examine the proposed small-diameter CFRP strands for shear strengthening of steel web girders. The considered parameters are the fiber orientations and number of layers of the CFRP strands. To simulate pure shear stresses acting on steel plate, the square plate specimen is rotated 45 degree and clamped to heavy steel frame which is subjected to tension load as schematically shown in Figure 9(a). The applied tension load to the steel frame induces equivalent shear forces along the edges of the steel test plate through the uniformly distributed pre-stressed bolts as shown in Figure 9(b). The shear forces along the edges of the specimen induced compression stresses perpendicular to the direction of the applied tension load and tension stresses parallel to direction of the applied tension load.

Figure 9: State of forces acting on the test plate

Two 2000 kN (440 kip) capacity hydraulic actuators are used to apply the tension load to the steel frame. The two hydraulic actuators are connected to the same controller to ensure equal loads from each actuator. Two highly stiffened spreader beams were especially designed to transfer the tensile load to the shear frame. The bottom spreader beam is pre-stressed to the strong floor to provide reaction equal to the applied load. Schematic sketch and view of the test setup is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: pure shear test setup

The steel plate is pre-stressed to the articulated built-up steel frames through series of high-strength bolts as shown in Figure 11. The forces induced in the steel frame are transferred to the test plate through friction-type connection provided by the bolts. The frame is made up of four very stiff steel plate legs, each consist of stiff short and long steel plates. Each two legs are connected using high-strength steel pins at the ends. The steel frames were specially designed to fail the test plate without permanent deformation.

Figure 11: Schematic 3D view and positions of the test plate and frames

The eighteen square steel plates included in this phase are given in Table 3. The CFRP strands are externally bonded in three orthogonal directions at an angle of 45° , 90° , and 0° relative to applied tension load using one and two layers of the HM CFRP strands on each side of the plate. Figure 12 shows configuration of each specimen including orientation of HM CFRP strands. A layer of the low-modulus polyurea putty will be used between the steel plate and the CFRP strands for all strengthened specimens. To provide confident in the collected data, duplicate specimens were used for each category. The control specimen is used as strengthened specimen with one layer and subsequently two layers of HM CFRP strands. The average percentage increase of the buckling load from each test will be used to determine the effectiveness of the proposed strengthening configurations.

Specimen ID	Set #	Height	Thickness	h/t	Fiber Orientation	No. of Layers
		mm (in.)	mm (in.)			
II-36-3/16-1-45-C	1	915 (36)	5 (3/16)	192	NO	NO
II-36-3/16-1-45-1HM					45°	1
II-36-3/16-1-45-2HM					45°	2
II-36-3/16-2-90-C	2				NO	NO
II-36-3/16-2-90-1HM					90°	1
II-36-3/16-2-90-2HM					90°	2
II-36-3/16-3-90-C	3				NO	NO
II-36-3/16-3-90-1HM					90°	1
II-36-3/16-3-90W-2HM					90°, 0°	2

Table 3: Shear strengthening test matrix

Figure 12: Schematic sketch of shear strengthening test matrix

Figure 13 shows the instrumentations used to capture behavior of the specimens. Vertical and horizontal strains at mid-point were measured using electrical resistance strain gages with a gage length of 5 mm (3/16 in.). Four Strain gages are attached to both faces of the control specimen, with two strain gauges on each face. Two vertical strain gauges are attached in direction of diagonal tension load and two horizontal strain gauges are attached in direction of the compression component. A total

of eight strain gauges are attached to the strengthened specimens at mid-point. Four strain gauges are attached to the base steel and the remaining four strain gauges are attached to the outer surface of the CFRP strand sheets. The overall out of plane lateral deformation of the steel plates is measured using five linear string potentiometers. Optotrak Certus® motion capturing system is also used. The motion capturing system measures a three-dimensional (3-D) coordinate system by the use of Infrared Emitting Diodes (IRED) attached to the specimen at points of interest. The IREDs were attached to the front face of the test specimens along with the vertical and horizontal centerlines and were spaced at 75 mm (3 in.). All instrumentations were connected to an electronic data acquisition system.

Figure 13: Specimen instrumentations, a) IREDs and strain gauges attached on the front face of test plate, b) string potentiometers and strain gauges attached to the back face

Test results of the control specimen (II-36-3/16-1-45-C) and strengthened specimen (II-36-3/16-1-45-1HM) are presented in this paper. The orientation of the HM CFRP strands of the strengthened specimen (II-36-3/16-1-45-1HM) has an angle of 45 degree with the applied tensile load. The total applied load versus measured horizontal and vertical strains at mid-point of the two specimens are shown in Figure 14(a) and Figure 14(b), respectively. Results indicate an increase of 32 percent in the load capacity before yielding of the steel of the strengthened plate compared to the control plate. The measured horizontal strains of the steel plate and the externally bonded CFRP, confirm the effectiveness of the CFRP in increasing the shear capacity of the plate. The measured vertical strain reveals slight effect of the CFRP strands in tension direction.

Figure 14: Applied load vs. steel strain of the plates under pure shear, a) horizontal strain, b) vertical strain

5. CONCLUSION

- i. The proposed small-diameter CFRP strands can significantly increase the flexural capacity of steel beams and totally eliminate de-bonding failure of the strengthening materials.
- ii. Use of small-diameter CFRP strands for uniaxial strengthening of steel plates is extremely effective in increasing the buckling capacity. The system does not de-bond up to failure. The proposed CFRP strengthening system is more effective for large slenderness ratios and by increasing the reinforcement ratio.
- iii. Preliminary test results of two specimens subjected to pure shear reveal effectiveness of proposed strengthening system to increase shear capacity and stiffness.

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